

SoTL in Civil and Structural Engineering Systematic Review Protocol

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1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review (PRISMA) 2020

1.1 Introduction

A transparent systematic review should present completely and accurately why it has been done, what has been done and what was found. The benefits of a systematic review are:

- They allow to identify future research priorities based on the synthesis of state-of-the-art knowledge in a certain field.
- Questions that cannot be addressed by individual studies can be answered by systematic reviews.
- Give a hint to future studies to rectify aspects of primary research identified on them.
- Provide answers to how and why a particular phenomenon occur based on the generation and/or evaluation of theories.
- They can generate or evaluate theories about how or why phenomena occur.

The PRISMA 2020 [1] methodology, although mainly developed and used in the medical and clinical sciences, could be also applied in engineering and education, as it provides guidance in methodologies to identify, select, appraise and synthesize the available literature. This document presents the protocol adopted to perform a systematic review for the SoTL in Civil and Structural Engineering following the checklist provided by PRISMA and guidelines of the PRISMA-P Explanation and Elaboration [2].

1.2 Protocol

The recommended items to address in a systematic review protocol according to the PRISMA methodology are presented in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 1. Administrative information

Title:	Identification Update	SoTL in Civil and Structural Engineering Systematic Review Protocol -
Registration:		In accordance with the guidelines, our systematic review protocol was registered in the Open Science Framework (OSF) Registries on May 09, 2023, registration number yztd3 [3].
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	Contributions	AJR did the conception and design of the study, wrote the protocol and search strategy, carried out the search, organized the data and created the database, performed the bibliometric analysis, did the synthesis of the literature, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript, revised the manuscript, approved the submitted version and contributed to obtaining the necessary funding to carry out this work. VP, MN,

Amendments	and WA supervised the work. All authors contributed to manuscript revision, read, and approved the submitted version. AJR, VP and MN have as well contributed to the obtaining of the necessary funding to carry out this work. In the event of protocol amendments, the date of each amendment will be accompanied by a description of the change and the rationale. See Annex A.
Support:	
Sources	This systematic review has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101066739.
Sponsor	The European Union funded this research.
Role of sponsor/funder	The European Union is funding this research. The funder is not involved in any other aspect of the project and will have no input on the interpretation or publication of the study results.

Table 2. Introduction.

Rationale:	<p>Peter Felten [4] offers five principles of good practice in SoTL, suggesting that SoTL is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inquiry focused on student learning. • Grounded in both scholarly and local context. • Methodologically sound. • Conducted in partnership with students. • Involves 'going public'. <p>According to Wankat et al. [5], "Most published studies have used surveys and quantitative research methods, approaches with which engineers tend to be relatively comfortable, but studies that use some of the qualitative methods characteristic of social science research have also begun to appear".</p> <p>This systematic review will particularly focus on the fields of Civil and Structural Engineering, for which (to the extent of knowledge of the authors), similar works have not been published yet.</p>
Objectives:	<p>The aim of this systematic review is to collect and synthesis state-of-the-art knowledge and information about current practices applied in the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning in Civil and Structural Engineering, as well as to indicate and highlight challenges, future trends, and opportunities on this topic. To this end, the proposed systematic review will answer the following questions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How do civil and structural engineering educators (Professors, Lecturers, Teaching Assistants, etc.) conduct and/or are involved in the scholarship of teaching and learning? 2. What are the benefits/incentives/outcomes (economic, professional, personal, etc.) of implementing a scholarship of teaching and learning for civil and structural engineering educators?

Table 3. Methods.

Eligibility criteria:	<p>Peer reviewed papers (as well as reviews and book chapters), published both in journals or in conferences, in the field of engineering, and containing the following keywords (and similar terms, namely: engineer and engineering, etc.) of interest will be eligible:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil Engineering. • Structural Engineering. • Scholarship of Teaching and Learning.
Information sources:	<p>Several information sources will be used, including Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar and the OsloMet Library which are important sources of online trustworthy scientific material. They index all the major Journals and Proceedings on Engineering Education, i.e., Review of Educational Research, Journal of Engineering Education, European Journal of Engineering Education, Journal of Civil Engineering Education, IEEE Transactions on Education, Global Journal of Engineering Education, International Journal of Engineering Education, International Journal of Continuing Engineering Education, Australasian Journal of Engineering Education, etc.</p> <p>The OSF Registry will also be searched to avoid duplicating studies under development.</p>
Search strategy:	See SoTL in Civil and Structural Engineering Search Strategy [6].
Study records:	
Data management	A bibliographic database with all the data from the found records in format csv, ris, and bib will be created and published through the open-source repository Zenodo.
Selection process	All records found in Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar (only the first 50 pages of results including the 500 more relevant works) and the OsloMet Library will be

	<p>screened including both title and abstract. In a second round, all shortlisted records will be screened including full text to assess their final inclusion/rejection from the systematic review. No blinding will be used during the screening process. Only records dealing directly with civil and structural engineering education will be included. The screening will be performed by the first author of manuscript. The work of the first author will be supervised by the main and a secondment supervisor as well as by the collaborator. It is expected that not many records will be found, thus, a single screener will be able to do the job thus avoiding reconciliation issues and ensuring the quality of the screening.</p>
Data items:	<p>Description of the main variables will be extracted from every included record. The extraction will be performed by a human and will be done in a single stage. A single extractor will be used, and it will be supervised by both supervisors and collaborator. No divergence extraction decisions are foreseen. As it is expected to include only a few records in the systematic review, a single extractor should be able to perform the work, thus reconciliation procedures will not be necessary, and the reliability will be assured by the triple supervision in place. Information about the extracted entities will be available within the manuscript of the systematic review itself. Furthermore, a preprint will be produced and made available online. A quantitative bibliometric analysis will as well be performed based on keywords co-occurrence and co-authorships.</p>
Outcomes and prioritization:	<p>The main variables of interest are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The methodologies applied in the scholarship of teaching and learning in civil and structural engineering education. • The incentives and/or benefits in place for the civil and structural engineering educators that implement a scholarship of teaching and learning.
Risk of bias in individual studies:	<p>The risk of bias and quality of individual studies will be assessed based on the prior experience and background knowledge of the authors of the review working on similar reviews on the past.</p>
Data synthesis:	<p>No meta-analysis is envisaged for the proposed systematic review.</p>
Meta-bias(es):	<p>No meta-bias assessment is planned for the proposed systematic review.</p>
Confidence in cumulative evidence:	<p>No confidence assessment plan will be used for the proposed systematic review.</p>

References

1. Page, M.J., et al., *The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews*. BMJ, 2021. **372**: p. n71 DOI: 10.1136/bmj.n71.
2. Page, M.J., et al., *PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews*. BMJ, 2021. **372**: p. n160 DOI: 10.1136/bmj.n160.
3. Jiménez Rios, A. *Scholarship of Teaching and Learning in Civil and Structural Engineering Registry*. 2023.DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/YZTD3>.
4. Felten, P., *Principles of Good Practice in SoTL*. Teaching & Learning Inquiry: The ISSOTL Journal, 2013. **1**(1): p. 121-125 DOI: 10.2979/teachlearningqu.1.1.121.
5. Wankat, P.C., et al., *The scholarship of teaching and learning in engineering*. Disciplinary styles in the scholarship of teaching and learning: Exploring common ground, 2002: p. 217-237.
6. Jiménez Rios, A., et al., *SoTL in Civil and Structural Engineering Search Strategy*. Zenodo, 2023 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7937754>.

Annex A

Table 4. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	12/10/2023	Initial version.

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